

**Cardioprotection with nebivolol in patients undergoing anthracyclines (CONTROL):
a randomized placebo-controlled trial**

Supplementary Material: Methods and Secondary Outcomes

Population

Patients with an established diagnosis of Breast Cancer (BC) or diffuse large B cell lymphoma (DLBCL), without history of cardiovascular disease and with normal left ventricular (LV) systolic function at baseline echocardiographic assessment, scheduled for first-line chemotherapy with anthracycline were eligible for inclusion. After echocardiographic screening and cardiological assessment, all patients signed a written informed consent.

All included patients underwent a cardiac magnetic resonance (CMR) at baseline and at 12-month follow-up, and were evaluated with cardiological assessment, electrocardiography, echocardiography and cardiac biomarkers sampling at baseline, and at 1, 6, and 12 months of follow-up.

Full details on the study protocol were previously published.¹ The trial is registered in the EudraCT registry (number: 2017-004618-24) and in the ClinicalTrials.gov registry (identifier: NCT05728632).

Randomization

Patients were randomly allocated, centrally using a web-based system, to nebivolol or equivalent placebo in a 1:1 fashion. The allocation sequence was computer-generated in randomly varying blocks, and stratified by type of malignancy (BC or DLBCL). The allocated treatment was started the

day before the first chemotherapy cycle and continued for 1 year. Patients, treating physicians, investigators, outcome assessors, and statistician were masked to the allocated treatment.

Primary and secondary endpoints

The primary endpoint was left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) reduction assessed by CMR at 12 months of follow-up. LVEF reduction was defined as the difference between LVEF at baseline and LVEF at 12 months follow-up (LVEF reduction = 12 months LVEF - Baseline LVEF).

The following secondary endpoints were prespecified:

- i) CMR parameters at 12-month follow-up: LVEF, myocardial fibrosis and edema, right ventricular systolic function, LV end-diastolic volume, LV end-systolic volume, LV mass;
- ii) Echocardiographic parameters at 1, 6 and 12 months: LVEF, LV diastolic function, right ventricular systolic function, LV end-diastolic volume, LV end-systolic volume;
- iii) Serum troponin and natriuretic peptides levels at 1, 6 and 12 months
- iv) All-cause mortality, cardiovascular mortality, myocardial infarction, cerebrovascular events, and hospitalization for heart failure at 12 months follow-up.

CMR assessment

CMR studies were analyzed independently offline by two expert investigators blinded to treatment allocation and outcome data. Images are anonymized and assessed randomly using a dedicated software (Circle CVI42 station-version-5.13.7; Circle Cardiovascular Imaging Inc. Calgary, Alberta, Canada) according to current recommendations of the Society for Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance.²

Echocardiography assessment

Transthoracic echocardiography was performed by two expert investigators blinded to treatment allocation and outcome data with a Vivid E95 (GE Vingmed Ultrasound, Horten, Norway) and a Vivid E70 (GE Vingmed Ultrasound, Horten, Norway), while off-line analyses and measurements were performed with TomTec Software (TomTec Imaging Systems GmbH, Unterschleissheim, Germany), according to American Society of Echocardiography/European Association of Cardiovascular Imaging recommendations.³

Biomarkers assessment

High-sensitivity troponin I (“Access” lab assay (Beckman Coulter Diagnostics, Brea, California, US)), B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP)(“Access” lab assay) and NT-proBNP (“Access” lab assay) were measured at baseline, 1 month, 6 months and 12 months.

Clinical outcomes

An independent Clinical Event Committee (CEC) reviewed and adjudicated all major adverse cardiac events according to the study protocol. Detailed definitions of adverse cardiovascular events have been published previously.¹

Statistical methods

The trial was designed to test the hypothesis of superiority of nebivolol as compared to placebo to prevent a 12-month reduction in LVEF assessed by CMR in patients with BC or DLBCL treated with anthracyclines. We estimated that the inclusion of 80 patients would provide >80% power to detect a difference of 5.0% in LVEF reduction^{4,5} using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) adjusted for baseline LVEF at a two-sided alpha of 0.05, assuming a standard deviation of 8.5%,⁶ a correlation between baseline and follow-up of 0.5, and an attrition rate of 5%.

All randomized patients were included in the primary analysis of clinical outcomes according to the intention-to-treat principle. Baseline clinical and demographic characteristics are summarized by mean and standard deviations or median and interquartile range for continuous variables and by frequency and percentages for categorical variables. The primary analysis of the primary outcome was based on an ANCOVA model, with LVEF at 12 months as dependent variable and treatment and LVEF at baseline as independent variables. Secondary binary/categorical variables will be compared between groups using a Chi-square or Fisher's test, and presented by randomized groups using frequencies and percentages. Secondary continuous outcomes will be compared between groups using ANCOVA model if baseline values are available, otherwise they will be compared using a student t-test, and presented by randomized group using means and standard deviations. For all continuous outcomes, if major deviations from normality are detected, we will consider using bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals and p-values or non-parametric tests. Survival curves for secondary clinical endpoints will be constructed for time-to-event variables using Kaplan-Meier estimates per randomized group. Subgroup analyses of the primary outcome will be done by type of malignancy and sex. Trial data will be maintained under the responsibility of the principal investigator. Analyses will be performed by an external analyst blinded to treatment allocation. No adjustments will be applied for multiple comparisons in secondary analyses. P-values will be two-sided.

References

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Figure 1. Study flow-chart.

Abbreviations: CMR, cardiac magnetic resonance.

TABLES

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the study population.

Variable	Nebivolol (n = 40)	Placebo (n = 40)
Demographics		
Age at recruitment, years	51.4 (13.6)	52.5 (14.6)
Female	29 (72.5)	27 (67.5)
Race		
Asian	1 (2.5)	0 (0)
White	39 (97.5)	40 (100)
Cardiovascular risk factors		
Body mass index, kg/m ²	23.9 (3.2)	23.5 (4.3)
Smoking habit		
No	23 (57.5)	25 (62.5)
Current	11 (27.5)	7 (17.5)
Ex-smoker	6 (15)	8 (20)
Arterial hypertension	7 (17.5)	9 (22.5)
Diabetes mellitus	2 (5)	1 (2.5)
Hypercholesterolemia	3 (7.5)	7 (17.5)
Familiar history of coronary artery disease	10 (25)	10 (25)
Oncologic History		
Type of cancer		
Breast Cancer	12 (30)	13 (32.5)
Diffuse large B cell lymphoma	28 (70)	27 (67.5)
Total cumulative dose of anthracyclines, mg/mq	316.0 (106.5)	299.2 (92.3)
Type of anthracyclines		
Doxorubicine	39 (97.5)	39 (97.5)
Epirubicine	1 (2.5)	1 (2.5)
Concomitant therapy with EGFR inhibitors	1 (2.5)	4 (10)
Concomitant chest radiotherapy	19 (47.5)	20 (50)
Total cumulative radiotherapy dose, Gray	28.8 (17.6)	30.0 (16.6)
Previous history of chemotherapy	1 (2.5)	0 (0)
Previous history of radiotherapy	1 (2.5)	1 (2.5)
Vital signs		
Systolic blood pressure, mmHg	122.9 (15.3)	128.5 (13.1)
Diastolic blood pressure, mmHg	74.1 (9.0)	77.1 (7.9)
Heart rate, bpm	76.3 (11.3)	74.5 (11.1)

Values are mean ± SD or n (%).

Table 2. Primary and Secondary End Points.

	Nebivolol	Placebo	Mean difference (95% CI)*	p-value
CMR				
LVEF, %				
12 months	59.5 (5.9)	57.6 (9.3)	1.2 (-2.1 to 4.5)	0.48
LVEDV, ml				
12 months	121.0 (26.7)	133.9 (40.2)	-7.7 (-19.5 to 4.1)	0.19
Indexed LVEDV, ml				
12 months	70.2 (11.6)	75.4 (15.6)	-3.3 (-8.6 to 2.0)	0.22
LVESV, ml				
12 months	51.5 (20.9)	60.1 (37.4)	-5.1 (-17.4 to 7.1)	0.40
Indexed LVESV, ml				
12 months	28.7 (6.8)	32.0 (14.8)	-2.2 (-7.0 to 2.5)	0.35
LV mass, g				
12 months	82.1 (29.0)	84.2 (25.6)	2.1 (-5.4 to 9.6)	0.57
Indexed LV mass, g				
12 months	47.6 (13.9)	48.4 (11.0)	0.9 (-3.2 to 4.9)	0.67
T1, ms				
12 months	1002.9 (34.0)	1008.6 (38.7)	-10.6 (-27.2 to 5.9)	0.19
T2, ms				
12 months	47.1 (3.7)	47.5 (3.7)	-0.2 (-1.9 to 1.4)	0.77
ECV, %				
12 months	27.2 (3.8)	28.1 (4.6)	-0.9 (-2.9 to 1.1)	0.39
Presence of LGE				
12 months	14%	14.8%	0.97 (0.27 to 3.40)	0.96
Mass of total LGE 5SD, g				
12 months	0.2 (0.6)	0.2 (0.8)	-0.0 (-0.3 to 0.2)	0.77
Percentage of LGE/myocardial mass 5SD, %				
12 months	0.2 (0.6)	0.2 (0.7)	0.0 (-0.2 to 0.3)	0.72
RVEF, %				
12 months	57.3 (6.4)	56.6 (10.3)	-0.0 (-3.6 to 3.5)	0.98
Echocardiography				
LVEF, %				
1	61.1 (4.0)	62.7 (4.5)	-1.8 (-4.0 to 0.4)	0.11
6 months	61.0 (4.2)	58.5 (7.3)	2.4 (-0.4 to 5.1)	0.084
12 months	60.0 (4.6)	58.5 (6.9)	1.4 (-1.4 to 4.1)	0.32
LVEDV, ml				
1	94.8 (21.9)	94.6 (20.7)	0.3 (-8.4 to 8.6)	0.98
6 months	93.4 (21.2)	96.1 (27.6)	-2.8 (-12.5 to 6.8)	0.55
12 months	92.7 (17.3)	97.2 (23.7)	-4.6 (-12.4 to 3.1)	0.23
LVESV, ml				
1	37.2 (12.0)	34.8 (10.3)	2.3 (-5.3 to 9.9)	0.51
6 months	36.3 (21.6)	44.5 (26.9)	-8.0 (-26.3 to 10.3)	0.36
12 months	40.7 (15.5)	41.7 (19.4)	-1.0 (-15.0 to 12.9)	0.87
E / mean E' (or E prime)				

1	6.1 (2.7)	6.8 (2.4)	-0.8 (-2.4 to 0.9)	0.34
6 months	6.9 (3.2)	6.9 (3.4)	-0.0 (-2.1 to 2.1)	0.98
12 months	6.3 (2.6)	6.3 (2.5)	0.0 (-1.5 to 1.5)	0.99
TAPSE, mm				
1	24.8 (3.3)	24.1 (3.6)	0.6 (-1.1 to 2.3)	0.46
6 months	24.7 (5.0)	23.2 (4.6)	1.4 (-1.0 to 3.7)	0.23
12 months	23.9 (4.0)	23.6 (4.5)	0.3 (-2.0 to 2.6)	0.81
Cardiac biomarkers**				
hs Cardiac troponin I, ng/L				
1	1.3 (1.6)	1.4 (1.4)	-0.0 (-0.8 to 0.8)	0.93
6 months	2.2 (1.1)	2.8 (1.3)	-0.6 (-1.2 to 0.0)	0.056
12 months	1.5 (1.3)	1.6 (2.1)	0.0 (-0.9 to 0.9)	0.97
BNP, pg/mL				
1	4.2 (0.8)	3.6 (0.7)	0.6 (0.2 to 1.0)	0.002
6 months	3.9 (1.0)	3.8 (1.0)	0.1 (-0.5 to 0.7)	0.73
12 months	3.7 (0.9)	3.7 (1.0)	-0.1 (-0.6 to 0.5)	0.79
NT-pro-BNP, pg/mL				
1	5.1 (1.0)	4.4 (0.9)	0.6 (0.1 to 1.1)	0.017
6 months	5.1 (1.0)	4.7 (1.1)	0.4 (-0.3 to 1.0)	0.22
12 months	4.8 (0.9)	4.7 (0.9)	0.1 (-0.4 to 0.5)	0.78

Abbreviations: BNP, B-type natriuretic peptide; CI, confidence interval; CMR, cardiac magnetic resonance; ECV, extracellular volume; LGE, late gadolinium enhancement; LV, left ventricle; LVEDS, left ventricular end-systolic volume; LVEDV, left ventricular end-diastolic volume; LVEF, left ventricular ejection fraction; RVEF, right ventricular ejection fraction; TAPSE, tricuspid annulus systolic excursion.

The primary analysis of the primary outcome is based on an ANCOVA model, with LVEF at 12 months as dependent variable and treatment and LVEF at baseline as independent variables. Secondary binary/categorical variables are compared between groups using a Chi-square or Fisher's test, and presented by randomized groups using frequencies and percentages. Secondary continuous outcomes are compared between groups using ANCOVA model if baseline values are available, otherwise they are compared using a student t-test, and presented by randomized group using means and standard deviations.

*: Mean difference between groups estimated using an ANCOVA model for continuous outcomes and risk ratio for binary outcomes.

** : Log-transformed.

Table 3. Adverse clinical events.

Adverse clinical event	Nebivolol	Placebo	p-value
All-cause mortality	0 (0.0%)	2 (5.0%)	0.49
Cardiovascular mortality	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.5%)	1.00
Myocardial infarction	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	-
Cerebrovascular events	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	-
Hospitalization for heart failure	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.5%)	1.00
CTRCD	2 (5.0%)	3 (7.5%)	1.00

Values are n (%).

Outcomes are compared between groups using a Chi-square test.

Abbreviations: CTRCD, cancer therapy-related cardiac dysfunction.